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DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN AI-BASED 3D-PRINTED ROBOTIC ARM

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Abstract

This paper presents the design and development of a 3D-printed robotic arm manufactured using PLA material. The arm components were modelled using CAD software and printed through FDM-based 3D printing. The robotic arm is integrated with artificial intelligence and with the help of OpenCV to identify object colours using a camera and perform pick-and-place operations accordingly. Structural analysis and load distribution of the arm were evaluated using MATLAB simulation to validate the design, and the obtained results were agreeable with simulation results and the variations in the results due to the dynamic nature of the system.

Keywords: Robotic Arm, Artificial Intelligence, Computer Vision, OpenCV, Colour Recognition, Contour Analysis, MATLAB, Simulink, Servo Control, Automation.

1. Introduction

In modern industries, automation and intelligent machine systems have turned out to be much indispensable with respect to accuracy, efficiency, and reliability. Robotic arm plays the core role in these applications because of their capability of performing repetitive and precise tasks with least human intervention. With the introduction of AI and computer vision, robotic manipulators now interpret the environment and respond to real-time visual information, and this greatly powered up their functionality. Object detection is an integral part of robotic manipulation, particularly in an environment where the component to be manipulated must be identified either by shape, colour, or size.

This paper deals with the design and development of a vision-based AI-enabled robotic arm to detect and pick up cylindrical objects. It uses OpenCV to perform color and contour-based shape detection. MATLAB/Simulink for the simulation of robot kinematics, and a servo-driven robotic arm for the physical manipulation of the detected object. In order to demonstrate an effective and affordable method for automated sorting and material handling operations, the system actually combines simulation, visual processing, and its hardware implementation. The suggested method improves robotic arms' flexibility in changing situations and is representative of the new developments in intelligent automation [1].

The structure of this paper follows with Section I, Section II introduces the methodology used in the proposed system. Section III discusses the brief description of the project including the mechanical configuration and the components used. Section IV explains the hardware requirements of the project, which includes implementation on both hardware and software components. Section V explains the kinematic modeling of a three-degree-of-freedom robotic arm. Section VI gives a description of the experimental results, which includes the scope and conclude the proposed work.

2. Methodology

The Figure 1 schematically represents the methodology of overall working flow of the AI robotic arm system, which depicts the interrelation of vision processing, simulation, control, and actuation units. The system has a starting point, which is the camera that captures images of the objects based on workspace with objects. Images are analysed by an object detection system that was created with OpenCV algorithm. The system uses a computer vision method to identify the items in the images, such as colour and contour detection. Following an object's identification, matching detection data is generated. [3].

Figure 1: Flow diagram

After that, the MATLAB/Simulink environment receives the detection data and uses it for simulation. This procedure verifies the accuracy of the robotic arm movement and the logic used for object detection prior to implementation. After that the ESP32 microcontroller, which is considered as the centralized control unit, receives the processed detection result. By interpreting the signals it receives, the microcontroller generate control signals for the robotic arm. Finally, these control signals enable joint mobility and object manipulation by controlling both the robotic arm and the gripper. The robotic arm is in control of tasks like selecting and positioning the detected cylindrical object. Then the Figure 1 illustrates a closed-loop system that integrates control, simulation, and computer vision [6].

2.1 Project description

This project focuses on the design and development of a AI based 3D Printed Robotic Arm for pick-and-place applications. Figure 2 represents the 3D printed and assembled model of Robotic arm. The main objective of the projects is to develop low-cost and efficient robotic system capable of identifying objects based on color and performing corresponding actions with the help of AI algorithms for autonomous decision making [4]. CAD software was used to model the robotic arm's components, and PLA was used in the Fused deposition modelling method for printing. The arms' structural behaviour and load distribution are investigated using MATLAB simulations, and computer vision is developed using OpenCV to recognize object colours using a Webcam. Colour-based detection and pick-and-place tasks are effectively completed by the designed robotic arm. Due to the system's dynamic nature, there are only minor differences between the findings and the simulated values.

Figure 2: Assembled Robotic arm

3. System Components

Several key elements that contribute to the development of a robotic arm;

3.1 Poly Lactic acid

Polylactic acid Robotic arm components are printed using FDM-based 3D machines using polylactic acid (PLA) as the structural material. Lightweight robotic applications may benefit from PLA's favourable combination of low density, sufficient tensile strength, and good stiffness [5]. By using PLA, the arm's overall mass is decreased, which improves system efficiency and positioning precision while reducing the torque demand on the actuators. Precise production of intricate geometries is made possible by its excellent dimensional stability and simplicity of printing. The ability of PLA components to sustain operational loads during pick-and-place operations is confirmed by structural analysis.

3.2 Servo Motor

The servo motors are employed to operate the joints of the robotic arm. In this Robotic system 4 servo motors are used in that Three are MG996R and one is MG90S and each servo motor controls a specific movement such as rotation, lifting, and grasping. The MG996R servo motor was selected due to its reliable performance and high torque. It is made up of aluminum 6061-T6 alloy, which increases the strength and durability during operation. These motors receive signals from the controller and move to the point within an angle accurately. This allows the robotic arm to perform smooth and precise pick- and-place actions.

3.3 ESP 32

The ESP32 is a robust microcontroller that powers the system's advanced processing. It supports Wi-Fi and Bluetooth, which helps in communication and data transfer. In this project, the ESP32 is used to handle vision-related tasks and AI processing. It works faster than Arduino and manage complex operations efficiently. The ESP32 also supports multiple sensors and peripherals at the same time. This makes it suitable for intelligent and real-time robotic applications.

3.4 Webcam

The webcam functions as the eyes of the robotic arm through taking images of objects placed in front of the device. Computer vision techniques are applied to these images in order to identify the color of the object. The microcontroller receives control signals based on the information collected, and it uses those signals to instruct the robotic arm to carry out the pick-and-place task. The webcam's real-time visual input enables reliable item identification and automatic operation [7].

3.5 MATLAB Simulation

A high-level programming language and software environment, MATLAB (Matrix Laboratory) is used for system simulation, data analysis, algorithm creation, and numerical computations. It provides effective techniques for addressing difficult mathematical problems fast and efficiently.

Figure 3: Steps in MATLAB

The Figure 3 explains the steps involved in creating Simulink model, and it is created to analyze load distribution in the robotic arm and to study the behavior and performance of the robotic system. The model enables the analysis of joint position, velocity, and torque and aids in visualizing the dynamic reaction of the arm under various payload situations. It helps optimize design and control parameters prior to real-time implementation by enabling safe testing and validation of the robotic system.

The robotic arm's base, linkages, joints, and payload are systematically assembled using Simscape Multibody blocks to form the MATLAB Simulink model. Rigid bodies are added to represent each robot link when the base is first defined as a fixed reference. Next, revolute joints that closely resemble the robotic arm's physical structure are added between the connections to enable rotating motion. Smooth and realistic joint actuation is made possible by applying motion and torque inputs to the joints through regulated sources. The joints are equipped with sensors that continuously detect torque, position, and velocity while in use. PS-Simulink converters are used to transform these signals into Simulink signals, and the scope block is used to collect the results.

Figure 4: Simulink model of Robotic arm

Figure 4 represents the Simulink model of a Robotic system and it is helpful for researching the way the motion and torque needs of the robotic arm are affected by various payloads and external loads. It finds crucial locations where more torque is needed and aids in the analysis of load distribution across joints. Before deploying the robotic arm in practical applications, the simulation offers a secure and effective method to assess system performance, improve design parameters, and confirm control procedures. Joint position, velocity, torque, and end-effector reaction responses are also obtained; they are utilized to examine the robotic system's overall stability, dynamic behavior, and motion correctness. and again the system block diagram is created to illustrate object recognition, image processing, microcontroller control, and robotic arm movement in MATLAB. A Simulink model for color detection is created using the MATLAB Function block, as shown in Figure 5. This model checks whether the input image contains a specific color. To improve the accuracy of color detection, the image is first converted from RGB format to HSV color space [8]. The model then determines whether the intended color is present by comparing the HSV values with a predetermined range. When the color is detected, the method returns 1, and when it is not, it returns 0. These results are displayed using Simulink's digital display blocks [9] [10].

Figure 5: Colour detection Simulink model

Once the complete system has been simulated, successful results have been generated for the robotic arm operation. Furthermore, a Simulink model for color detection was developed, and the results are accurate.

4. Kinematic modelling for the developed robotic arm

The kinematics of a robotic arm can be described using either forward kinematics or inverse kinematics. In this project, the position of the end effector is determined using forward kinematics and the given joint settings. The robotic arm is geometrically composed of the waist, shoulder, elbow, and wrist joints, each of which has one degree of freedom.

4.1 Forward Kinematics

A Kinematics of Forward Using the set of joint-link parameters, forward kinematics determines the end-effector's position and orientation in relation to the specified reference frame. In this study, forward kinematics is implemented using geometric approaches. One of the fundamental techniques used in robotics to determine a robotic manipulator's forward kinematics is the geometric technique. This method uses the geometric relation between the robotic arm's lengths and angles to determine the end-effector's position. The end-effector's position is determined using the robotic arm's dimensions and the sine and cosine functions of the angles [11].

Assume,

$$\theta_1 = 45^\circ, \theta_2 = 110^\circ$$

$$L1 = \text{Length of the Link 1} = 15\text{cm}$$

$$L2 = \text{Length of the Link 2} = 15\text{cm}$$

$$X = L1 \cdot \cos\theta_1 + L2 \cdot \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2)$$

$$Y = L1 \cdot \sin\theta_1 + L2 \cdot \sin(\theta_1 + \theta_2)$$

X-position:

$$x = 0.15(0.7071) + 0.15(-0.9063)$$

$$x = -0.0298 \text{ m}$$

Y-position:

$$y = 0.15(0.7071) + 0.15(0.4226) \quad y = 0.1695\text{m}$$

$$(x, y) = (-0.0298\text{m}, 0.1695\text{m})$$

Figure 6: Block diagram

The Figure 6 represents the use of the geometric approach for forward kinematics problems in a two-jointed planar robotic arm with two rotational joints. The planar robotic arm has two rigid links with a length of 15 cm, joined together with two revolute joints. The robot has a fixed base, with all movements taking place within the two-dimensional X-Y plane.

The arm's first joint is rotated by an angle of 45° (θ_1) with respect to the base reference frame, thus placing the first link. The second joint is rotated by an angle of 110° (θ_2) with respect to the first link, thus fixing the orientation of the second link and the end effector. The position of the end effector is calculated based on the two joint angles, with the two links' known lengths. The calculated position of the end effector is $(-0.0298\text{m}, 0.1695\text{m})$ in Cartesian coordinates, as illustrated in Figure 5. The two coordinate axes represent the reference frames used for positioning the end effector.

5. Result and Discussions

The robotic system is effectively simulated using a MATLAB Simulink model, which enables detailed analysis of its dynamic behavior and overall performance. In addition, the integration of AI allows the robotic system to accurately detect and identify target objects using OpenCV-based image processing algorithms. From the simulation, joint velocity, joint torque, and end-effector response plots are obtained to evaluate the robotic system's performance.

Figure 7 represents the joint position-time response, from A to B (0–1 s), both joints remain at zero angular position because the ramp input is not yet applied, there is no movement observed during this interval. From point B onwards, once the ramp input begins, both joints start moving. Joint 1 increases gradually with a moderate slope, indicating a slower response. It continues to rise steadily, reaching approximately 0.78 rad at point D (4 s). In contrast, Joint 2 exhibits a steeper slope, moving faster than Joint 1. Its angular position increases more rapidly, reaching a higher value of about 1.75 rad at point C (4 s). This shows that Joint 2 responds quicker and achieves greater displacement than Joint 1 over the same time interval.

Figure 7: Joint Position-time Response

Figure 8: Velocity-time Response

The velocity-time response is shown in Figure 8. Joints 1 and 2 are not moving from A to B. During this period, their velocities are zero. This indicates that there is no motion instruction in Simulink and the robotic arm is at rest. The system is ready to go. The motion begins at point B. The velocities rapidly rise from B to C for Joint 2 and from B to D for Joint 1. Joint 1 achieves about 0.25 rad/s, whereas Joint 2 rapidly reaches about 0.65 rad/s. This occurs when a ramp input is applied, causing the joints to begin moving right away. Joint 2 travels at a steady speed from C to E. The joint has reached steady motion and is moving smoothly when the velocity remains constant. Joint 1 also travels at a constant rate from D to F, although more slowly than Joint 2. This facilitates the regulated and coordinated movement of the robotic arm. The graph generally shows three phases: the arm is at rest, it begins to move abruptly, and subsequently both joints move steadily.

Figure 9: Torque-time Response

Figure 9 represents the Torque-time response, From A to B, the torque of both Joint 1 and Joint 2 is zero. The robotic arm does not move during this period, and the motors do not require any effort. This is the initial resting state in Simulink when no motion command is used. There is no resistance or strain on the joints because they are motionless. The motion begins at point B, and the torque abruptly rises to a positive value from B to C for Joint 1 and B to D for Joint 2.

This increase in torque is required to initiate motion and overcome the links' initial resistance and inertia. Joint 1's torque is somewhat higher than Joint 2's, indicating that it takes more work to start moving. The torque values begin to decrease from C to E and D to F. This occurs because less torque is needed to keep the joints moving once they are in motion. The torque progressively decreases and approaches zero since the

motors no longer require a lot of effort.

The End Effector Position-time response is shown in Figure 10. The Z position exhibits a smooth and roughly linear increase from -0.30 m at the start of the motion to about -0.12 m at the end of the 10-second time, while the X and Y positions will remain constant at -0.02 m and 0.15 m, respectively. This behavior indicates that the end effector is traveling upward at a nearly constant speed along the Z direction under control.

Figure 10: End Effector Position-time Response

Comparison between the theoretical calculations and the simulation results is presented in the Table 1 below. These results are obtained by considering a load mass of 25 grams. The comparison aids in determining the way the analytical values match the MATLAB/Simulink simulation.

Table 1: comparative analysis

SI no.	Parameters	Theoretical		Simulation	
		Joint 1	Joint 2	Joint 1	Joint 2
1	Angle (Degree)	45	110	44.6	100.26
2	Torque (Nm)	0.083	0.069	0.12	0.18
3	Position of End Effector (m)	x	y	x	y
		-0.0298	0.1695	-0.02	0.15

Joint 1 exhibits the same joint angle values in simulation (44.6°) and analytical (45°), indicating that the model is accurate for this joint. System dynamics and computational simplifications may be the cause of Joint 2's slightly larger difference between simulation (100.26°) and analytical (110°). Due to perfect computations and dynamic effects like gravity and inertia included in the simulation, slight differences between the theoretical and simulated results are anticipated. Therefore, extra torque is required in simulation. The end effector position's X and Y values in the simulation are close to the theoretical values. Slight variances are caused by changes in joint angles and dynamic effects during simulation.

Conclusion:

During the system's initial simulation test, the Simulink robotic arm and colour detection models both performed as intended. In the real scenario, the robotic arm used OpenCV-based computer vision to precisely identify objects with smooth, controlled movements, confirming accurate actuation and kinematic response in real time.

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